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Thermal evaluation of two advanced air-cooling systems for different Spanish climate zones

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1. Introduction

Approximately 36% of the world's final energy consumption is attributed to heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC) systems in buildings, with nearly 40% of total CO₂ emissions being contributed by them. [1]. In the context of Nearly-Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) operating in hot weather conditions, the adoption of efficient HVAC technologies presents an interesting alternative to traditional air-cooling systems that rely on direct expansion units [2]. In addition, the climate change scenario, with its progressive rise in outdoor air temperatures, has adverse implications for both human health and the energy consumption of HVAC systems in buildings [3].

The use of efficient air-cooling systems based on the evaporative cooling technology could be a possibility to achieve the objective of NZEB and thermal comfort. According to several research works, a strong correlation exists between the Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) value of a dew-point indirect evaporative cooler (DIEC) and outdoor weather conditions, that is, the higher the outside air temperature and the lower the outside air humidity, the higher the EER value [4].

The aim of this work was to evaluate the thermal performance of a DIEC and a desiccant DIEC (DW-DIEC) in terms of supply air conditions and seasonal EER (SEER), under a prediction of different weather conditions in Spain for 2050. Annual energy simulations under four different Spanish weather conditions – Almeria, Barcelona, Caceres, and Logrono - were carried out using a DIEC model and a DW-DIEC model and *TRNSYS17* software. The *CCWorldWeatherGen* tool was also used to obtain the predictions of the weather conditions for these four Spanish cities in the year 2050.

2. Methodology

Two air-cooling systems utilizing indirect evaporative cooling technology were investigated with regards to their supply air (SA) conditions and energy efficiency, under different Spanish weather conditions. The first system was composed of a dew-point indirect evaporative cooler (DIEC), whose empirical model was obtained by Romero-Lara et al. [5], while the second system studied was composed of a desiccant dew-point indirect evaporative cooler (DW-DIEC), as depicted in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively.

Fig. 1. Schematic of DIEC.

Fig. 2. Schematic of DW-DIEC.

Regarding the DIEC system, a single inlet air stream with three different air states was used: outdoor air (OA), supply air (SA), and exhaust air (EA), as illustrated in Fig. 1. However, the DW-DIEC system featured two inlet air streams owing to the presence of a desiccant wheel (DW). These five different air flows in DW-DIEC were: two outdoor air flows (OA), a supply air flow (SA), and two exhaust air flows (EA), as depicted in Fig. 2. Therefore, the main difference between both innovative air-cooling systems was the additional dehumidification capacity of the DW-DIEC system. The DIEC system controlled the supply air temperature, while the DW-DIEC system controlled both the supply air temperature and humidity ratio, as depicted in Fig. 2.

According to the climatic classification of the Basic Document HE Energy Saving – CTE [6], four cities of Spain were selected in this work: Almeria, Barcelona, Caceres, and Logrono. In addition, a widely used tool in scientific studies, *CCWorldWeatherGen* [7], was used to generate climate scenarios in 2020 and 2050. Table 1 presents the average values of OA temperature, $T_{OA,avg}$, and OA humidity ratio, $\omega_{OA,avg}$, for each climatic zone throughout the cooling period. It should be noted that two humid areas, A4 and C2, exhibited a $\omega_{OA,avg}$ value above $11 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, while two dry areas, C4 and D2, displayed a $\omega_{OA,avg}$ value below $9 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, see Table 1.

Table 1. Spanish climatic zones studied under the 2020 and 2050 weather conditions.

CTE-HE classification	Zone type	City	2020		2050	
			$T_{OA,avg}$ [°C]*	$\omega_{OA,avg}$ [g·kg ⁻¹]*	$T_{OA,avg}$ [°C]*	$\omega_{OA,avg}$ [g·kg ⁻¹]*
A4	Hot-humid	Almeria	24.1	11.3	25.1	11.6
C2	Warm-humid	Barcelona	22.9	11.3	23.8	11.7
C4	Hot-dry	Caceres	25.3	7.4	26.7	7.2
D2	Warm-dry	Logrono	23.4	8.4	24.5	8.5

*Mean values throughout the cooling period, that is, the period in which the T_{OA} value was higher than $18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

In order to analyse the seasonal energy performance, multiple energy simulations were conducted using *TRNSYS17* software [8]. These simulations incorporated the DIEC and DW-DIEC models, along with meteorological predictions for the year 2050 from the four different cities. Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER) values were calculated according to Eq.1:

$$SEER = \frac{\int \dot{Q}_{cooling} dt}{\int \dot{W} dt} = \frac{Q_{cooling}}{W} \quad (1)$$

Where $Q_{cooling}$ is the annual cooling energy and W is the annual electrical-energy consumption for the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems, during the cooling period of each one of the selected Spanish cities.

3. Results and analysis

Different OA and SA temperature values, as well as OA and SA humidity values, for DIEC and DW-DIEC were obtained for the four selected cities under the 2050 climatic scenario. The case studies of Caceres and Barcelona are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively.

Fig. 3. OA and SA conditions of DIEC and DW-DIEC for the Caceres climatic conditions in 2050.

The T_{OA} values for Cáceres exceeded $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the summer season, a period in which the T_{SA} values of DW-DIEC ($T_{SA,DW-DIEC}$) were lower, see Fig. 3. Due to the ω_{OA} values around $10\text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ during this summer period, the T_{SA} values of DIEC ($T_{SA,DIEC}$) were higher than the $T_{SA,DW-DIEC}$ values, see Fig. 3. Therefore, the increase in outdoor temperatures resulted in an enhancement of the sensible cooling capacity for both DIEC and DW-DIEC systems. However, the presence of medium-high values of outdoor air humidity had a detrimental effect on the cooling capacity of the DIEC system.

In the case of Barcelona, the highest T_{OA} values were around $35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, see Fig. 4. In addition, the range of ω_{OA} values during the months from June to October was between $10\text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ and $15\text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, see Fig. 4. Due to these high outdoor humidity values, the T_{SA} values of both the DIEC system and the DW-DIEC system were higher than for the dry climate of Cáceres, see Fig. 3. However, the $T_{SA,DW-DIEC}$ values were also lower than the $T_{SA,DIEC}$ values, due to the reduction in humidity ratio of the DW-DIEC system, Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. OA and SA conditions of DIEC and DW-DIEC for the Barcelona climatic conditions in 2050.

The OA and SA conditions for Cáceres and Barcelona were shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively, as a representation of the Spanish dry and humid climatic zones selected in this work, see Table 1. However, the thermal behaviour of the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems was studied for the four cities: Almería, Barcelona, Cáceres, and Logroño, under the 2050 weather conditions. Fig. 5 shows the values of $T_{OA,avg}$, $\omega_{OA,avg}$ and Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER) for both advanced air-cooling systems during the cooling period of each city.

Fig. 5. SEER values of DIEC and DW-DIEC for Almería, Cáceres, Barcelona, and Logroño in 2050.

SEER values for DIEC were between 2.2 and 4.6, while the SEER values for DW-DIEC were between 2.8 and 7.2, as indicated in Fig. 5. It can be observed that for both air-cooling systems, the highest SEER values were obtained in the hot-dry climate zone of Cáceres, 4.6 for DIEC and 7.2 for DW-DIEC, and warm-dry climate zone of Logrono, 4.5 for DIEC and 5.2 for DW-DIEC, see Fig. 5. Therefore, both DIEC and DW-DIEC presented better thermal behaviour under climatic conditions with the ω_{OA} value below $10 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, see Fig. 5. High humidity values, above $10 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, negatively influenced the SEER value of DIEC given its non-desiccant capacity. High humidity values also negatively influenced the SEER value of DW-DIEC since the SEER index focuses only on sensible cooling capacity. However, the DW-DIEC system manages to cool and dehumidify the inlet air. So, both the DIEC system and the DW-DIEC system could be an interesting alternative to traditional air-cooling systems in terms of thermal comfort and energy savings.

4. Conclusions

In the current climate scenario, there is growing concern about the continued increase in outdoor air temperatures. The increasing demand for sustainable solutions necessitates the exploration of efficient air-cooling systems. In this work, the thermal performance of two air-cooling systems utilizing indirect evaporative cooling technology were examined. The supply air (SA) conditions and SEER values for both the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems were evaluated under the projected 2050 climatic conditions in four cities in Spain.

The key findings of the analysis were as follows:

- The rise in outdoor air temperatures led to an improvement in the sensible cooling capacity of both the DIEC and DW-DIEC systems. However, the presence of outdoor air humidity values above $10 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ had a negative impact on the cooling capacity of the DIEC system.
- The supply air temperature values of DW-DIEC were lower than the supply air temperature of DIEC in all cases, due to moisture reduction prior to being treated by the DIEC.
- High SEER values were obtained for DIEC and DW-DIEC under dry climatic conditions: 4.6 for DIEC and 7.2 for DW-DIEC in Cáceres weather conditions and 4.5 for DIEC and 5.2 for DW-DIEC in Logrono weather conditions.

As a result, both the DIEC system and the DW-DIEC system present themselves as compelling alternatives to conventional air-cooling systems due to their potential for providing enhanced thermal comfort and energy savings.

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